

Sustainable groundwater-based date palm farming: Lessons from a multi-stakeholder dialogue in Kebili Region, southern Tunisia

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Abstract

The sustainability of groundwater-based date palm systems in Kebili Region, southern Tunisia, is challenged by the continuous increase of farmed areas under private initiatives called “extensions”, irrigated from illegal boreholes and the development of photovoltaic panels used for pumping the underlying aquifers. Actors have identified the overexploitation of groundwater resources as the main threat, but there has been no discussion on how to respond to this concern. This is resulting from the complexity of interactions between different actors’ strategies, diverse decision-making processes across sectors and spatial levels. Therefore, a common representation of the issues and of actors’ interventions at different scale, is a prerequisite to facilitate the emergence of more collaborative and sustained groundwater use. This study investigates an integrated approach that helps the creation of conditions for dialogue between groundwater actors. The developed approach integrates a spatial analysis tool, surveys and a multi-actor participatory process. The main output of the multi-actor participatory process is the initiation of a dialogue including stakeholders representing the diversity of farming situations, public sectors, and spatial level. The study underlines that combining spatial analysis knowledge and a participatory process catalysed stakeholder dialogue and enabled the identification of measures and the creation of policy-based knowledge towards sustainable groundwater management.

Keywords: Groundwater Governance, Participatory Mapping, Multi-actor Process, Palm Date, Sustainability.

Purpose

Global groundwater resources are under pressure, with effects on producers, food and fibre production systems, communities and ecosystems (Molle & Closas, 2016). Groundwater-based agriculture sustainability cannot be answered by just one actor but rather using a multi-actor approach perspective. Indeed, it involves different actors such as researchers, farmers, entrepreneurs, regional and national organisations and results from their complex “systemic interactions” (Belmans, 2018). Biophysical research has

clarified the challenges and proposed a series of technological solutions. However, achieving a sustainable use of groundwater is fundamentally a governance challenge, that spreads over a continuum from local- to global-scale. Many knowledge gaps exist to assess change drivers and their consequences that compromise the development of both optimal local adaptations and national, regional, and global mitigation objectives (Berger et al., 2019). The real challenge is dealing with systems that are not only cross-scale but also dynamic, creating important uncertainties about stakeholders' responsibilities. Despite all these difficulties, the adaptive governance literature reports evidence that well-structured dialogue involving policy makers, scientists, and the concerned public can lead to improved natural resource management (Folke et al. 2005, Olsson et al. 2006). However, questions about how to organize and what methods and tools can support the adaptation decision-making process still remain open in the literature. This paper contributes to the existing literature, expands the frontier of socio-technical analysis on the transition to sustainable agriculture. The aim of this paper is to investigate an integrated approach that helps to motivate participation of relevant groundwater actors and to encourage their interactions and dialogue.

Methodology

Case study

The groundwater considered in this study provides water supply mainly from two confined aquifers: the Continental Intercalaire (CI) and the Terminal Complex (CT). The southwest region constitutes the area which took 40% of the volume of water pumped in Tunisia during the year 2021. In the governorate of Kebili more than 765 Mm³ of which 47% is extracted by illegal pumping (DGRE, 2021) due to the expansion of irrigated palm groves. These private initiatives, called "extensions", developed on uncultivated collective lands, outside the old palm groves (Mekki et al., 2022). The total surface area of these extensions increased from 7,000 ha in 1996 to 32,700 ha in 2020, while that of the old palm groves, called Public Irrigated Perimeters, did not exceed 10,500 ha in 2018 (Mekki et al., 2021).

Implementation of an integrated framework

This study follows an integrated approach with the stepwise process developed by Wieczorek and Hekkert (2012) including complementary quantitative and qualitative methods to account for the complex multi-level nature of the analysis: 1) stakeholders' analysis of key actors to involve, 2) a quantitative spatial analysis approach, in-situ measurements and a data collection from interviews and surveys with territorial actors, and 3) a series of multi-actor participatory workshops that allowed to collectively identify prevailing dynamics and future scenarios (Figure 1).

Stakeholders' analysis

The identification of the relevant stakeholders to be involved was an iterative process, where stakeholders are added along the process. Semi-structured interviews, expert opinion, focus group or a combination of all methods were used for stakeholder analysis (Reed 2008). The actors were identified and were considered to have an influence on or to be influenced by the groundwater farming systems. Stakeholders were invited to engage in the study development and activities with different levels of participation based on their roles. These levels ranged from specific

consultations to active involvement in the project (e.g. hosting demonstrations, facilitating meetings, field visits etc....).

Spatial analysis

Methods included diverse spatial analysis tools, interviews, and participatory workshops to retrace the spatial, social and temporal boundaries of Kebili oases transformation i) surveys, exchange questionnaire- based quantitative tools, where stakeholders are requested to individually answer questions, ii) face-to-face meetings (such as seminars, workshops, focus group, community events, or field visits), iii) participatory monitoring, the engagement of farmers, in the design of water monitoring for the irrigation; (iv) participatory training approach and demonstration farm. We use maps as a tool for peer-to-peer interpretation and dialogue.

Figure 1: Main steps of the integrated approach used.

Multi-actor participatory approach

In this study, a multi-actor participatory process was implemented to engage a dialogue and build a joint vision of the on-going overexploitation of groundwater resources that promotes the co-construction of visions for the future and the actions needed to achieve them. As groups worked in separate workshops producing separate results, the fact that their priorities were not compatible was addressed. We mixed subgroup discussion with plenary debates to avoid such problem (Munaretto et al., 2014). A total of nine participatory workshops were organized between March 2021 and May 2022 that aim: (1) to motivate participation of relevant actors to the situation diagnosis (2) to create space for actors' innovations development (3) to provide to actors' institutional information such as regulations, laws, norms and, (4) to encourage actors' interactions and dialogue. Stakeholders' discussions ended with proposed options, which were a compromise that reflected stakeholders' preferences and engagement to implement them. This methodology uses maps for actors to identify and draw the main dynamics of the territory and discuss their

knowledges and the future scenarios. Based on the identified dynamics, the actors imagined and drew a possible spatially explicit scenario for the region. A series of actions towards a sustainable future of farming systems in the area was identified. Identified actions should be feasible and possible to implement at present. Each participatory workshop involved a skilled facilitator to engage participants and encourage dialogue. The constitution of the database and the data processing were carried out with QGIS software and Microsoft Excel.

Findings

Decisions on groundwater governance are influenced by multiple overlapping /nested functions, and redundant centres of power and factors that interact across temporal and spatial scales. The identified relevant stakeholders were categorised into four categories: water users (farmers, associations), regional public entities, national public entities, and research institutions. During the workshops, the actors were really engaged in the process. The main findings of the present research show that the dynamics most often described by actors are not leading to a sustainable future of the Kebili landscape (Figure 2) including the extension development and the impact on the drainage.

Figure 2: Examples of dynamics drawn during the participatory workshops. Generalisation of extension development, urban sprawls on old oasis and their environmental impacts.

The multi-actor participatory process ended with options and measures for a sustainable groundwater, which aimed to achieve a compromise that reflected stakeholders' engagement and preferences with regard to the spatial extension (table 1).

Several responses were proposed: i) revising public policies, ii) setting up adaptive legislations, and iii) implementing regulation measures. These responses aim to enable the control of water abstraction, while accounting for tensions between nationwide regulation policies and socio-environmental local contexts. This involves in particular:

Reinforcing the role of water user association (GDAs according to their local acronym in French) to enhance their administration and financial autonomies when relaying governmental measures.

Enhance information flow and collaboration across scales for transformations to sustainability in collective action.

A path of innovation that included promoting innovative irrigation practices an optimising water supply and drainage systems that mitigate soil salinization and waterlogging. A call for creating or improving extension services to better inform and build the capacities of farmers, so that these can implement "good practices" in terms of photovoltaic uses.

Build a regulatory framework that promote cooperation amongst farmers and links short-term agricultural development objectives with long-term water resource preservation objectives.

Table 1. Overview of the main dynamics/issues and measures towards sustainable future explored during the multi-actor participatory process.

Thematic	Dynamics	Factors change of	Measures towards sustainable future	Actors involved	Strategies for engagement/scale
Historical oasis	Water shortage High-cost water pumping Drainage problem	Complex institutional of water management policies Dysfunction of collective water management Over-irrigation situation	Collective water management Enhance performance solar energy irrigation Assess date palm water needs Improving extension services for farmers Reclamation of drainage water	CTV Research CRDA GDA	Informing/ Legislative Organizational National/local National/local demonstration/field visit
Extensions	Overexploitation of the groundwater Degradation of water resources Drainage/salinization problem Solar Energy	Little cooperation between stakeholders' Lack of communication Development of illicit wells Problems of solar irrigation	Participatory workshops Solar energy profitability studies Awareness days for farmers on the use of solar energy Subsidies	Farmers, APIA Research CRDA Ministries	Informing/ Legislative Organizational National/local Organizational/ local

GDA -Group of agricultural development (water users association), CTV-Local agricultural extension units; CRDA-Regional Centres for Agricultural Development; APIA - Agricultural Investments & Promotion Agency.

Practical Implications

Groundwater governance includes the involvement of multiple actors across different institutional and spatial levels. Successful water governance needs the coordination of these actors and their actions. In order to effectively solve conflicts between groundwater users, and to reduce pressures to groundwater sustainability, authorities need tools dynamically coupling social, and physical dimensions that will assist in making more proactive, and evidence-based management decisions. The integration of different kinds of knowledge can be used as a guiding tool to build links between all stakeholders engaged in the transition towards sustainable groundwater “economies” through (i) improving the visibility of farmers' problems, and (ii) informing stakeholders about the spatial impacts of the different activities. Spatial data allow discussions to emerge about

groundwater governance challenges. It also made it possible to identify avenues for improving the dialogue. This is related to the capacity to process information/data and to connect it to the experiences from past changes and responses, and to facilitate adaptive and innovative responses. The final decision in charge of the decision-maker(s) should be based both on the results of participation and of technical and spatial analysis, allowing to assess the feasibility and impacts of the proposed solution.

Theoretical Implications

The analytical proposed framework enabled a) a better understanding of the interactions among actors and between actors and their environment in complex systems and b) contributed to addressing the conceptual gaps in terms of studying the interconnection and interdependence of different governance levels.

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